

Essay: Comparative analysis of basic English and Spanish sentence patterns

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Abstract

This article examines the comparative analysis of basic English and Spanish sentence patterns that a learner should have. The main objective of the study is to be able to get acquainted with the use of the parts of speech in both English and Spanish, particularly in effectively using the parts of speech in both languages, in understanding the words in English having two or more word equivalents into Spanish, and in realizing the importance of learning English which can be applied in communication functions needed in Spanish settings. Some basic sentence patterns were discussed to understand more in the use of Spanish language, through the combinations of different parts of speech: noun, pronoun, verb, adjective, and adverb. Differences in translating English into Spanish were revealed in the given sentences from this study.

Keywords: *Comparative analysis; English; Spanish; basic sentence patterns.*

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Introduction

Facing language learning challenges is one of the great concerns of students. The use of English, especially at the tertiary level, has intensified both in oral and written communication functions. The emphasis placed on the rhetorical principles of grammatically constructed sentences that would lead to paragraph development continuously prevails. Explanations of linguistic structures towards communicative competence are so vital that students are really obliged to read English materials, especially those used in classroom interactions (Galloway et al., 2020).

Students who find difficulty understanding and following the different principles might develop correct habits of speaking and writing if they exert more effort in learning language seriously. Effective English, applied in academic undertakings—both oral and written activities—would basically require knowledge of correct and needed sentence constructions (Arbesman et al., 2010). Through the use of correctly structured sentences that eventually lead to an understanding of grammar composition, comprehension should be thoroughly taught and learned at a higher and more productive level.

The use of foreign languages in certain courses in college has been given importance with the belief that students with proficiency in English and other foreign languages can have higher fulfillment and more productive accomplishments (Lingard et al., 2021). It is this reality that prompted the researcher to focus on the comparative analysis of basic English and Spanish sentence patterns (Stockwell et al., 1965). Basic sentence patterns necessitate understanding the complexity and sophistication of learning a language like English and Spanish that have similarities in sentence constructions, which can help students use these two languages, especially in classroom undertakings (Callahan, 2004; Prior et al., 2007).

Objectives of the Study

This study has the following objectives:

- To be able to get acquainted with the use of the parts of speech in both English and Spanish;
- To be able to use the parts of speech in both languages;
- To be more conscientious in using the verbs in both languages;
- To know certain similarities in sentence construction;
- To have critical observations on the similarities of the two languages;
- To understand the words in English having two or more word equivalents;
- To speak and write even in simple Spanish sentences; and
- To realize the importance of learning English which can be applied in communication functions needed in Spanish settings.

Familiarization with Spanish Pronouns

Students need to familiarize themselves with the pronouns in Spanish, which are very important in the conjugations of verbs and sentence constructions (Barcelona & Soriano, 2004; Schwartz et al., 2007; Taranov, 2012).

Table 1. Spanish pronouns

Pronouns (in Spanish)	English Equivalent
<i>Yo</i>	I
<i>Tu</i>	You (sg. Familiarity)
<i>El / Ella</i>	He / She
<i>Usted</i>	You (sg. Formality)
<i>Nosotros</i>	We
<i>Vosotros</i>	You (pl. Familiarity)
<i>Ellos / Ellas</i>	They
<i>Ustedes</i>	You (pl. formality)

There are examples of Spanish sentences for learners to get acquainted with:

English

Yo estudio mis lecciones.
Tu estudias tu lecciones.
El / Ella estudia otras lenguas.
Usted estudia lecciones dificiles.
Nosotros estudiamos muchas lecciones.
Vosotros estudiais otras lenguajes.
Ellas / Ellos estudia español.
Ustedes estudian bien.
El / Ella lee las letras / cartas en la pizarra.
Usted compra papel y cuadernos.

Spanish

I study my lessons.
 You study your lessons.
 He / She studies other languages.
 You study difficult lessons.
 We study many lessons.
 You study other languages.
 They study Spanish.
 You study well.
 He / She reads the letters on the board.
 You buy paper and notebooks.

English sentences with transitive verbs also require direct object/s. The following sentences can be translated into Spanish.

English

She eats fruits.
 You write letter.

Spanish

Ella come frutas.
Tu escribes cartas. / Usted escribe cartas.

He / She reads the letters on the board.
You buy paper and notebook.

*El / Ella lee las letras en la pizarra.
Usted compra papel y cuaderno.*

Basic Sentence Patterns

Six basic sentence patterns were discussed to understand more in the use of Spanish language.

1. **N/P V_{INT} (Noun/Pronoun + Intransitive Verb)**. An intransitive verb in English is an intransitive verb in Spanish. The verb is complete in itself and does not require a direct object. It may be followed by a word or phrase that functions as an adverb.

English

A baby cries.
They cry.
He cries bitterly.
The students dance at the auditorium.

Spanish

*Un bebe llora.
Ellos / Ellas lloran.
El llora amargamente.
Los alumno bailan en el auditoria.
Las alumnas bailan en el auditoria.*

2. **N/P V_{TN} (Noun/Pronoun + Transitive Verb + Noun)**. Transitive verb requires a direct object. It is also transitive in Spanish.

English

We read books.
Lita eats fruit salad.

Spanish

*Nosotros leemos libros.
Lita come Macedonia.*

3. **N/P V_L (Noun/Pronoun + Linking Verb)**. There are sensory words that can be used as linking verbs.

English

Candies taste sweet
Music sounds pleasant
Flowers appear beautiful
The girls feel amazed.
The weather seems cloudy.
She looks pretty.
The wind sounds horrendous.
Ampalaya tastes bitter.
Fried chicken tastes delicious.

Spanish

*Las confiterias gustan dulces.
La musica esta agradable.
Las flores aparecen hermosas.
Las niñas sienten asombrada.
El tiempo aparece nublado.
Ella mira hermosa.
El viento esta horrenda.
El amargoso tiene sabor amargo.
Pollo gusta dalicioso.*

4. **N/P LBe_V (Noun/Pronoun + Be Verb)**. Be verbs in different forms are used as linking verbs in many English books. Some examples are the following:

English

(Be + Noun) Liza is a teacher.
Ms. Delos Reyes is a nurse.
You are an accountant.

(Be + Adjective) She is intelligent.
She was sick last week.

(Be + Pronoun) You are mine.
We are here.

Spanish

*Liza es maestra.
Srta. Delos Reyes es enfermera.
Usted es contable / contador.

Ella es inteligente.
Ella estuvo enferma la semana pasada.

Ud es mio.
Estamos aqui.*

(Be + Adverb) They are here.
They were at the seminar yesterday.

Ellos / Ellas estan aqui.
Ellos estuvieron en la seminario ayer.

5. **N/P V_T N Adj (Noun/Pronoun + Noun + Adjective)**. The pattern N/P V_T Noun Adjective is most commonly used because only very few verbs are used in this pattern.

English

Spanish

The jury considered Lucas guilty.
Dr. Grecia pronounced the patient comatose.

El jurado considerará Lucas cupado.
Dr. Grecia declaró el paciente comatose.

6. **N/P V_T N N (Noun/Pronoun + Transitive Verb + Noun + Noun)**. Pattern N/P V_T N N is not commonly used because only very few verbs are used in this pattern.

English

Spanish

The classmates of Rushell elected him
president of the class.
People give the victims donations.

*Los companeros de clase de Rushell
le eligio presidente de clase.*
El gente dan donations a las victimas.

Basically, the sentence patterns in English and Spanish have similarities because the parts of speech used linguistically and communicatively have similar meanings, as analyzed. The sentences are easy to analyze, especially if the components of the sentences have words that are found in the dictionary. However, there are verbs in sentences that are difficult to analyze. The word *look* has 23 forms because of the preposition added to it. They become idiomatic expressions, and their use primarily depends on their content. Some examples are:

English

Spanish

look after
look ahead
look away
look down
look for

attender
hacia adelante, mirar al futuro
apartar la mirada
bajar la mirada
buscar

There are several meanings of the verb phrase or phrasal verb in English that do not have equivalent basic Spanish sentence patterns. The fact that such phrasal verbs are very difficult for the students to use in sentences in English makes it even more difficult for them to use them in Spanish sentence constructions.

Since there are English words that can be used as verbs, nouns, and adjectives, sentences needing verbs and adjectives in Spanish should be analyzed fully and deeply. Words like *look* with a preposition following it do not have exact Spanish sentence patterns. English basic sentence patterns, which have many verbs used, do not have Spanish equivalents; hence, no comparative analysis between the two sentence patterns should be included.

The very complicated verb tenses, such as present perfect and past perfect tenses, should not be included because only the present tense indicative mood of the verbs is discussed in Spanish (Xhaferraj & Hasa, 2014). Vocabulary words that are not found in the English-Spanish dictionary should be avoided, for they will cause much difficulty for students. English verbs, which have several meanings when they are followed by prepositions, should not be compared with Spanish verbs (such as in the use of the word *get* in Table 2).

Table 2. Meanings of the word *get*

English Words	Meaning	Spanish Equivalent
Get across	to be clear	<i>atravesar</i>
Get ahead	to be successful, to proceed	<i>adelantarse, salir adelante</i>
Get together	to collect, assemble	<i>reunir, juntar</i>
Get around	to become known	<i>conocido</i>
Get back	to revenge	<i>vengar</i>
Get out	depart	<i>salir, desviarse</i>
Get over	recover from	<i>recuprar, formar de nuevo</i>
Get up	to rise	<i>levantarse</i>
Get in	to arrive	<i>llegar</i>

Some of the English verb phrases do not have exact Spanish equivalents. English derivation has a complete derivation; a verb, noun, adjective, and adverb do not have exact Spanish equivalents. For example, when a person translates the verb *recede* in Spanish, which means to move back or withdraw, it may be derived as *retroceder* in some contexts. In the case of the sample noun *recession*, it can be translated as *recesión*. For the adjective *recessive*, the Spanish equivalent may be *recesiva* (if a person is a female) or *recesivo* (if a person is a male), while for the adverb *recessively*, this can be described as *recesivamente*. This means that some Spanish words can be borrowed from the original English words or phrases.

Differences in translating English into Spanish are revealed in the following sentences: In English, the noun or pronoun as subject should be indicated in the sentence. Such examples are:

English

Marie studies foreign language.
She learns important lessons from the course.
I go to school regularly.
You understand different concepts.

Spanish

Marie estudia lenguaje extranjera.
Ella aprende lecciones importantes del curso.
Voy a la escuela regularmente.
Comprendes (sg. fam.)
Comprende (sg. form.)
Comprendéis (pl. fam.)
Comprenden (pl. form.)

Another difference is that if the direct object is a pronoun, it is found after the verb in a transitive verb. A sample sentence can be seen below:

English: We teach him some difficult lessons.

Spanish: *Nosotros le enseñaremos algunas lecciones difíciles.*

In Spanish, the subject is never omitted. The verb or predicate depends on the subject with regard to its number, tense, and gender.

English: They go to church every Sunday.

Spanish: *Van a la iglesia cada Domingo.*

The use of *van* as the verb or predicate may also mean that the subject is *Ellos*, *Ellas*, or *Ustedes*. The verb form already contains the number and tense.

Recommendations

Suggestions were made in relation to learning the basic sentence patterns in English and Spanish. Students, especially those wanting to learn Spanish for their professional advancement, when they go to Spanish-speaking countries, have to internalize the following:

1. Acquaint yourself fully with the verb forms and their conjugations (in Spanish), as well as the different tenses of the verbs in English.
2. Be able to apply the tenses in a variety of sentences.
3. Analyze critically sentence constructions that do not have an exact equivalent in Spanish as regards sentence order and syntactical arrangement.
4. Acquire a rich vocabulary in English and Spanish for their oral and written communication functions.
5. Enhance linguistic skills by using the parts of speech comprehensively.
6. Learn to write and speak in both languages by familiarizing yourself with the basic patterns.
7. Persevere in transforming and effectively lengthening basic sentence patterns, leading to composition writing.
8. Rationalize the value of learning a foreign language, which may contribute greatly great deal towards professional and social prestige.
9. Be aware that adjectives in Spanish are usually found after the nouns modified.
10. A direct object in a sentence using transitive verb is found after the verb (e.g., We read many books).

References

- Arbesman, S., Strogatz, S. H., & Vitevitch, M. S. (2010). Comparative analysis of networks of phonologically similar words in English and Spanish. *Entropy*, 12(3), 327-337. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e12030327>
- Barcelona, A., & Soriano, C. (2004). Metaphorical conceptualization in English and Spanish. *European Journal of English Studies*, 8(3), 295-307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1382557042000277403>
- Callahan, L. (2004). *Spanish/English codeswitching in a written corpus* (Vol. 27). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Galloway, E. P., Uccelli, P., Aguilar, G., & Barr, C. D. (2020). Exploring the cross-linguistic contribution of Spanish and English academic language skills to English text comprehension for middle-grade dual language learners. *AERA Open*, 6(1), 2332858419892575. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2332858419892575>
- Lingard, L., Cristancho, S., Hennel, E. K., St-Onge, C., & van Braak, M. (2021). When English clashes with other languages: Insights and cautions from the Writer's Craft series. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 10(6), 347-351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-021-00689-2>
- Prior, A., MacWhinney, B., & Kroll, J. F. (2007). Translation norms for English and Spanish: The role of lexical variables, word class, and L2 proficiency in negotiating translation ambiguity. *Behavior Research Methods*, 39(4), 1029-1038. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193001>
- Schwartz, A. I., Kroll, J. F., & Diaz, M. (2007). Reading words in Spanish and English: Mapping orthography to phonology in two languages. *Language and Cognitive Processes*, 22(1), 106-129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01690960500463920>
- Stockwell, R. P., Bowen, J. D., & Martin, J. W. (1965). *The grammatical structures of English and Spanish* (Vol. 4). University of Chicago Press.
- Taranov, A. (2012). *Spanish vocabulary for English speakers – 9000 words*. T&P Books.
- Xhaferraj, M., & Hasa, D. (2014). A comparative overview of the verbal system in Albanian and Greek. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 4(6), 103-110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5901/jesr.2014.v4n6p103>